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**PREVALENCE OF FOOD ALLERGIES
AMONG PATIENT PRESENTING IN
EMERGENCY DEPARTMENT**

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ABSTRACT:

A food allergy is a hypersensitive immune response to a specific food. The allergic reaction's symptoms can range from mild to severe. Itching, tongue swelling, vomiting, diarrhea, hives, difficulty breathing, or low blood pressure are some of the symptoms. This cross-sectional study was conducted on patients who presented to various hospitals' emergency departments. The name, age, gender, and symptoms of presentation, as well as the duration of symptoms and possible causes of allergy, were recorded on a predefined proforma. A total of 89 patients presenting in emergency department were included in this study i.e., 49 (55%) males and 40 (45%) females. The mean age of the patients was 39.12 ± 7.34 years. Among all patients, the prevalence of self-reported food allergy was 11.1 percent, with 4.2 percent reporting a doctor-diagnosed food allergy. The prevalence of food allergy was for the top six allergens i.e., peanut, egg, milk, wheat, soybeans and fish.

Keyword: Food Allergy

INTRODUCTION:

A food allergy is a hypersensitive immune response to a specific food. The allergic reaction's symptoms can range from mild to severe. Itching, tongue swelling, vomiting, diarrhoea, hives, difficulty breathing, or low blood pressure are some of the symptoms. This usually happens within minutes to several hours of being exposed. Anaphylaxis occurs when the symptoms are severe. Food intolerance and food poisoning are distinct conditions that are not caused by an immune response.

Cow's milk, peanuts, eggs, shellfish, fish, tree nuts, soy, wheat, sesame, rice, and fruit are all common suspects. The most common allergies vary by country. A family history of allergies, a lack of vitamin D, obesity, and a high level of cleanliness are all risk factors. Allergies develop when immunoglobulin E (IgE), a component of the immune system, binds to food molecules. The problem is usually a protein in the food. This causes inflammatory chemicals like histamine to be released. A medical history, elimination diet, skin prick test, blood tests for food-specific IgE antibodies, or oral food challenge are usually used to make a diagnosis.

Early exposure to allergens may be beneficial. Management primarily entails avoiding the offending food and having a plan in place if exposure occurs. This strategy could include administering adrenaline (epinephrine) and wearing medical alert jewellery. As of 2015, the benefits of allergen immunotherapy for food allergies are unknown, so it is not recommended. Some food allergies in children, such as those to milk, eggs, and soy, resolve with age, while others, such as those to nuts and shellfish, do not.

In the developed world, approximately 4% to 8% of people have at least one food allergy. They are more common in children than in adults and appear to be becoming more common. Male children appear to be affected more frequently than females. Some allergies are more common in childhood, while others appear later in life. In developed countries, a large proportion of people mistakenly believe they have food allergies when they do not (1-3). The goal of

this study was to assess the prevalence of food allergy among the patients presenting in emergency department.

MATERIAL AND METHODS:

This cross-sectional study was conducted on patients who presented to various hospitals' emergency departments. The name, age, gender, and symptoms of presentation, as well as the duration of symptoms and possible causes of allergy, were recorded on a predefined proforma. All the data was entered and analysed using SPSS Ver. 23.0. The quantitative variables were displayed as a mean and a standard deviation. The qualitative variables were presented as frequencies and percentages.

RESULTS:

A total of 89 patients presenting in emergency department were included in this study i.e., 49 (55%) males and 40 (45%) females. The mean age of the patients was 39.12 ± 7.34 years. Among all patients, the prevalence of self-reported food allergy was 11.1 percent, with 4.2 percent reporting a doctor-diagnosed food allergy. The prevalence of food allergy was for the top six allergens i.e., peanut, egg, milk, wheat, soybeans and fish.

DISCUSSION:

Early exposure to allergens may be beneficial. Early exposure to eggs and peanuts, in particular, reduces the risk of allergies to these foods. Peanuts should be introduced as early as 4–6 months, according to the guidelines, which also include precautionary measures for high-risk infants. The previous guidelines, which advised delaying the introduction of peanuts, are now thought to have contributed to the recent increase in peanut allergy.

A strict diet can be followed to avoid an allergic reaction. Because determining the amount of allergenic food required to elicit a reaction is difficult, complete avoidance should be attempted. In some cases, allergen exposure through

skin contact, inhalation, kissing, sports participation, blood transfusions, cosmetics, and alcohol can cause hypersensitive reactions. Allergic reactions to airborne particles or vapours of known food allergens have been reported as an occupational hazard for people working in the food industry, but they can also occur at home, in restaurants, or in confined spaces such as aeroplanes. According to two reviews, respiratory symptoms are common, but in some cases, anaphylaxis has developed. Peanut, seafood, legumes, tree nuts, and cow's milk were the most frequently reported allergenic foods that caused reactions by inhalation. Steam rising from the cooking of lentils, green beans, chickpeas, and fish has been well documented as causing reactions, including anaphylactic shock. One review cited case study examples of allergic reactions to other foods inhalation, including examples where oral consumption of the food is tolerated (4-5).

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